

Mammadova Salima Aliqulu

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor

Department of Therapeutik Dentistry

Rustamov Elshan Anvar

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Orujov Ahmad Vagif

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine Assisetet

, Department of Therapeutik Dentistry

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969405>

IMPACT OF SYSTEMIC DISEASES ON PERIODONTIUM

Abstract.

Periodontology is experiencing an era of research interest in all issues and problems related to the etiology, risk factors for the development of periodontal diseases, and the study of the pathogenesis of the disease in relation to the condition of the whole organism. Periodontal diseases are polyetiological diseases of nearby dental tissues, the resulting interactions of local, systemic and other factors, characterized by the progression of a process that leads to the complete loss of structures that support the tooth.

Key words: *dental plaque, periodontal disease, systemic pathology, development of periodontal diseases, periodontal tissue, disease*

The interaction between systemic pathology and periodontal diseases has been confirmed by numerous epidemiological and clinical studies [8]. According to the classification of periodontal diseases developed by us based on many years of experience in research and practical work, analysis of foreign and domestic literature (L.N. Dedova, 2002), periodontitis associated with systemic pathology is represented by a form - symptomatic periodontitis [3]. Symptomatic periodontitis is a group of periodontal diseases in which pathological changes in periodontal tissues are a symptom of systemic diseases. The term "system" is characterized as a set of tissues, organs, their parts, representing a certain unity and connected to perform a common function. Systemic - related to the system [6]. Systemic diseases cause changes in tissues or organs that create conditions for the development of periodontal diseases. Those. There are factors that have a profound effect on the body, including: the vascular system, physiological reactions, the immune system, the inflammatory response, tissue regeneration. Therefore, systemic problems can modify the microflora of dental plaque, sensitivity to the disease, clinical manifestations of periodontal pathology, disease progression, and response to treatment. Systemic diseases can lead to rapid destruction of periodontal tissues [7]. Symptomatic - being a symptom, indicative. Symptom (Greek symptoma coincidence, sign) is a characteristic manifestation, a sign of a disease. Symptomatic periodontitis includes periodontal diseases against the background of endocrine imbalances, diseases of the hematopoietic, respiratory, cardiovascular systems, gastrointestinal tract, HIV infection, Down's disease, etc. Symptomatic periodontitis as a manifestation of systemic diseases in comparison with other pathological processes in periodontal tissues accompanied by more complex and profound disturbances in the biological system of the periodontium. It is distinguished by the peculiarity of its course, the active involvement of the entire complex of periodontal tissues, an inadequate response to traditional treatment, and the need for active maintenance

therapy. Diagnosis, treatment planning and implementation of therapeutic measures for patients with symptomatic periodontitis against the background of systemic pathology require deep professional knowledge from the dentist and constructive cooperation with clinicians and patients. Periodontal diseases are bacterial infections caused by plaque microorganisms. This causative role has been confirmed both experimentally in various studies and by the fact that the accumulation of dental plaque in the gingival area leads to the development of gum inflammation. Eliminating plaque helps reverse the condition and restore gum health. In the early 1970s, Loe and colleagues studied the prevalence of periodontal disease in Sri Lanka. The study was conducted among tea plantation workers who never brushed their teeth. The workers were divided into age groups from 14 to 46 years, and were followed over a 15-year period. As expected, the prevalence of gingival inflammation was high, with rapid progression of attachment loss in 8% of the population and moderate progression in 81%. Particular attention was drawn to the fact that 11% of workers were not found to have progression of periodontal disease (no more than gingivitis), despite the accumulation of a large amount of dental plaque. The researchers explained the obtained data by the fact that the workers examined were infected with various microorganisms or had different levels of sensitivity to the microflora of the oral cavity. Today, more than 300 species of bacteria are known that can exist in the oral cavity, and only a few, even a few or combinations thereof, cause the tissue destruction observed in periodontal diseases. Specific bacteria associated with periodontal diseases include microorganisms that have a high degree of connection with the etiology of periodontitis - *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Bacteroides forsythus*; having a moderate degree of connection - *Campilobacter rectus*, *Eubacterium nodatum*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Peptostreptococcus micros*, *Streptococcus intermedius*, *Treponema denticola* [9]. Microbial plaque is an initial

factor in the development of the inflammatory process in periodontal tissues. Although dental plaque is a necessary component in the development of periodontal disease, its absolute role is currently questioned. For example, there is reliable evidence that the level of oral hygiene of the population has improved, but the prevalence of various forms of chronic periodontitis has remained unchanged over the past 20 years. The efforts of dentists to motivate and instruct patients regarding oral hygiene, improving the quality of hygiene products, and increasing the use of additional oral hygiene products have led to a positive effect - a decrease in the plaque index and a decrease in the prevalence, mainly of gingivitis. Consequently, bacteria are a necessary but not sufficient condition for the development of periodontitis, because the etiology of periodontitis involves three main interrelated factors that exist even before the disease manifests itself: the body as a whole; environmental factors contributing to the development of the disease; state of periodontal biological barriers. The resulting interaction of these factors leads to inadequate inflammation of periodontal tissues, in which there is a pronounced disturbance of microcirculation. This leads to destruction of the connective tissue structures of the periodontium and alveolar bone with the clinical manifestation of symptomatic periodontitis. It should be noted that systemic factors do not affect the formation of a periodontal pocket, but they can influence the rate of increase in its depth, increasing the degeneration of periodontal connective tissue structures. Systemic diseases modify all forms of periodontal disease.

DIABETES MELLITUS AND PATHOLOGY OF PERIODONTAL TISSUE EPIDEMIOLOGY OF THE DISEASE Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a disease caused by absolute or relative deficiency of insulin, accompanied by impaired metabolism of proteins, fats and gradual damage to all organs and systems. It is a complex disease with varying levels of systemic and dental complications depending on metabolic control, the presence of infection, and relevant demographic factors. Over the past decades, there has been a steady upward trend in the incidence of diabetes mellitus throughout the world: in 1995, about 100 million people suffered from diabetes mellitus, and in 1999 there were already more than 120 million such patients. In Western European countries, patients with diabetes mellitus make up from 3 to 9% of the population. According to expert forecasts, by 2025 the number of people with diabetes may reach 250 million people [6]. Diabetes causes early disability and high mortality, ranking third after cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Medical complications associated with diabetes include chronic renal failure, retinopathy and cataracts, diabetic foot syndrome, polyneuropathy, and hypertension. The prevalence and severity of medical and dental complications may depend on the type of diabetes. About 10–20% of all diabetics have type 1 diabetes (insulin-dependent), which is characterized by the rapid onset of symptoms, the virtual inability to produce insulin, and the difficulty of controlling its metabolism. This type of diabetes develops in individuals with a genetic predisposition to diabetes-inducing factors such as a viral in-

fection or others that trigger the development of destructive autoimmune reactions. About 90% of patients are usually diagnosed before the age of 21. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (non-insulin-dependent) is usually found in patients over 40 years of age, is often associated with excess weight, has a slower onset of symptoms, and is less severe. The number of patients increases annually: according to 1999, there were 128 thousand people (1200 per 100 thousand population), in 2003 - 137 thousand people (1385 patients per 100 thousand population). Almost 80% of patients have non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM), 10–15% suffer from insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM). In 5–10% of cases, diabetes mellitus is caused by various diseases [9].

CLINIC OF PERIODONTAL LESIONS IN DIABETES MELLITUS Oral health complications most often associated with diabetes are gingivitis, periodontitis, tooth loss up to edentia, pathology of the oral mucosa. Patients with poorly controlled diabetes may complain of decreased salivation and a burning sensation throughout the mouth or tongue. Patients taking oral hypoglycemic drugs may suffer from xerostomia, which predisposes to the development of candidiasis. According to various authors, periodontal tissue damage occurred in 51–70% of patients with diabetes mellitus [9]. Differences in periodontal tissue involvement in patients with type 1 or type 2 diabetes may be due to varying degrees of glycemic control, age, duration of disease, level of dental care, susceptibility to periodontal disease, and smoking. People with type 1 diabetes have an increased risk of developing periodontal disease with age and the severity and duration of the disease. Changes in periodontal tissues in patients with diabetes begin already in childhood and puberty. Most studies confirm that young patients are less resistant to gum inflammation, and the course of the disease is more destructive with the formation of periodontal pockets. A number of studies have examined the relationship between diabetes and periodontitis. Interesting results were obtained from a study of the Arizona Indians of the Pima tribe (3219 people), among whom 45% of the population suffered from type 2 diabetes. In all age groups studied, the prevalence of periodontitis was 3 times higher than in patients without diabetes. As a result of these studies, it was revealed that patients with diabetes are characterized by a higher prevalence of infectious lesions of periodontal tissues, a severe course with the formation of deep periodontal pockets, progression of tooth mobility, and frequent recurrence of periodontal abscesses [8]. These and other epidemiological studies confirm that diabetes increases the risk of developing periodontitis. Significant differences in the condition of the periodontium were revealed in diabetic patients with controlled and uncontrolled glycaemia. With controlled glycaemia, there is less plaque and destructive changes in the periodontium are less pronounced. Periodontal destruction in both types of diabetes largely depends on the duration of the underlying disease and on the ability of the patient and physician to keep glycemic levels in balance. The classic picture of periodontal disease in a patient with undiagnosed or

uncontrolled diabetes is the presence of multiple periodontal abscesses, leading to rapid periodontal destruction [9]. The X-ray picture depends on the severity of the process and the effectiveness of diabetes treatment, and is characterized by destruction of interalveolar septa of various types, funnel- and crater-like type of resorption of bone tissue of the alveolar process, which does not extend to the body of the jaw [1]. However, in this category of patients, symptomatic periodontitis may be accompanied by a horizontal type of alveolar bone resorption. According to international studies, the prevalence of complete adentia among patients with type 2 diabetes is 15 times higher than among the healthy population. Therefore, periodontal disease has been called one of the complications of diabetes mellitus. Despite the fact that the relationship between diabetes mellitus and periodontal diseases has been known for more than 40 years, the mechanism of development of complications from periodontal tissues still remains the subject of study. The mechanism of development of periodontitis is similar to other complications accompanying diabetes mellitus. Studies have shown that hyperglycemia is the main cause of diabetic damage to the eyes, kidneys, and nerves. Glucose in increased concentration combines with other molecules, stimulates chemical reactions, which result in the formation of enzyme-free glycosylation products. Large molecules accumulate in tissues, leading to vascular disorders and damaging their normal functions. It is assumed that such reactions also occur in periodontal tissues, which have good permeability to glucose. Reduced resistance to periodontal bacteria in patients with uncontrolled glycemia may be due to impaired neutrophil chemotaxis and phagocytosis, which are characteristic of diabetes. Thus, in patients with type 1 diabetes, a significant number of Capnocytophaga bacterial strains were identified from periodontal pockets (up to 24% of the total microflora). A similar predominance of putative pathogens: *Prevotella intermedia*, *Campilobacter rectus*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, related to the development of chronic periodontal diseases in adults, was found in periodontal lesions in patients with type 2 diabetes against the background of insufficient metabolic control. There are several etiopathogenetic mechanisms for the occurrence of diabetic periodontitis: 1. Impaired function of polymorphonuclear leukocytes (neutrophils) - the cells of the first line of defense of the human body: disruption of chemotaxis, adhesion, phagocytosis and the mechanism of elimination of microorganisms. As a consequence, a decrease in the resistance of periodontal tissues to infection, its progression, and the occurrence of acute inflammatory processes (especially in patients with diabetes that is difficult to control). 2. Glycosylation of tissues due to chronic hyperglycemia, which leads to enzyme-free glycosylation of many proteins. As a result, there is an accumulation of advanced glycosylation end products, which play a major role in the development of diabetic complications. These products are predominantly formed on the walls of blood vessels, causing disruption of their functioning, but can occur in almost all tissues of the body. By binding to the cell surface of macrophages and monocytes, they

lead to a damaged cellular phenotype, resulting in increased release of cytokines. Damaged macrophages are also unable to fully participate in regeneration. This may explain the decreased tissue healing capacity found in diabetic patients. 3. Microvascular changes: the basement membrane of small vessels thickens as a result of enzyme-free glycosylation of extracellular matrix components and intracellular proteins by glucose. The resulting products accumulate in tissues, in the walls of small vessels, reducing their permeability and elasticity, and hyalinosis develops. These changes can lead to a narrowing of the lumen of blood vessels, interfere with the transport of substances through the vascular wall, impair the diffusion of oxygen, promoting oxygen stress in periodontal tissues, preventing the excretion of metabolic products and maintaining inflammation. The binding of enzyme-free glycosylation products to the vascular endothelium can induce coagulation, leading to the formation of microthrombi and vasoconstriction, and as a result, tissue nutritional disorders. 4. Impaired collagen metabolism: in a hyperglycemic environment, due to decreased production or utilization of insulin, the growth, proliferation and matrix synthesis of collagen by osteoblasts and fibroblasts of the gums and periodontal ligament may be reduced. A decrease in collagen synthesis by fibroblasts, a violation of its renewal and regeneration also occurs with collagen in the walls of blood vessels. 5. Violation of the basic properties of oral fluid: due to a decrease in the rate of salivation, an increase in the concentration of glucose in the oral fluid, a decrease in pH occurs, a decrease in the content of lysozyme, and disturbances in the composition of immunoglobulins. 6. Impaired tissue regeneration and healing in diabetic patients is the cumulative effect of numerous metabolic, cellular and vascular disorders: decreased collagen synthesis by fibroblasts; increased destruction of collagen by collagenase; glycosylation of existing collagen. 7. Increased susceptibility to osteopenia in diabetes: increased resorption of bone tissue by osteoclasts with increased glucose concentration, activity of periopathogenic microorganisms, increased release of cytokines, impaired bone metabolism due to impaired blood supply, impaired collagen synthesis. Osteopathy is one of the manifestations and complications of diabetes. Just like other complications of diabetes, periodontal disease depends on the compensation of diabetes. Patients with poor blood glucose control experience more severe periodontal disease leading to tooth loss than those with good control [20, 21]. Biochemical studies have shown that all of the above factors depend on the concentration of glucose in the blood and can be regulated by appropriate therapy. Control of glucose levels contributes to the partial restoration of impaired functions. In fact, patients with well-controlled diabetes are no more likely to suffer from periodontal disease than people without diabetes. Good compensation of diabetes reduces the risk of developing periodontal diseases [20]. Some authors [9] consider the main risk factors for periodontal disease in diabetes to be: 1) type 1 diabetes mellitus, because Periodontal diseases of this type occur earlier and therefore more often reach pronounced, destructive forms; 2) the duration of diabetes, which increases the

risk of developing periodontitis in the same proportion as the risk of developing other complications of diabetes (retinopathy, nephropathy); 3) poor metabolic control of diabetes (blood glucose levels). An important risk factor in the occurrence of periodontal diseases is smoking [18]. Smokers are 5 times more likely to develop periodontal disease than non-smokers. In diabetic patients who smoke, the risk of developing periodontal disease with destruction of the supporting tissues of the tooth increases 20 times. As the severity of diabetes increases, there is an increase in the destruction of periodontal tissue. Periodontal infection, in turn, affects the course of diabetes mellitus [19]. It is now known that chronic infectious diseases, such as periodontal disease, can impair diabetes control due to systemic effects on the body. The exact nature of this complex interaction is not fully understood. Researchers have also studied the effect of periodontal infection on metabolic control. Acute viral or bacterial infection is known to contribute to the development of insulin resistance by impairing blood glucose control. Factors such as stress, increased body temperature, increased levels of insulin antagonist hormones (cortisol, growth hormone, glucagon) play an important role in the occurrence of insulin resistance during the infectious process. Chronic Gram-negative infections, in which microorganisms produce bacterial toxins, have the same effect. To confirm this hypothesis, a special treatment regimen was developed for patients with symptomatic periodontitis associated with diabetes, in a group with poorly controlled glycemia. As a result of the treatment, which included curettage of periodontal pockets and removal of subgingival tartar, the concentration of glycosylated hemoglobin in the blood, which is an indicator of diabetes compensation, significantly decreased in a short time. These results suggest that chronic periodontal infection impairs glycemic control and elimination of this infection may improve metabolic control in patients with diabetes [8]. WHO defined diabetes mellitus as a problem of all ages and all countries. Extensive programs have been launched throughout the world to combat diabetes and its complications. Currently, diabetologists around the world consider education of patients with diabetes to be the cornerstone in achieving maximum efficiency of the treatment process for this disease [6]. In "diabetes schools," patients are taught self-control in order to: 1) maintain stable normoglycemia; 2) preventing the development of late complications of diabetes leading to disability; 3) adaptation to a full and active life in society. The difficulties in treating periodontal diseases in patients with diabetes are explained by the peculiarities of its course and the nature of complications, the involvement of various organs and anatomical formations in the pathological process. The literature contains rather contradictory information about the methods of dental treatment of patients with periodontitis associated with diabetes mellitus [9, 20]. Treatment and prevention of periodontal diseases should be based on the cooperation of the dentist, patient and endocrinologist.

The treatment plan is based on the main stages used in the treatment of periodontitis (preparatory, corrective, surgical, supportive). The main goal of diabetes therapy carried out by an endocrinologist is to improve the compensation of carbohydrate metabolism (elimination of hyperglycemia, maintaining normoglycemia), which can prevent the development and progression of diabetic complications, including periodontal ones. The main goal of treatment of symptomatic periodontitis against the background of diabetes, carried out by a dentist: to motivate the patient in the need for self-help to monitor oral hygiene and control diabetes; achieving and maintaining a good level of oral hygiene; prevention of progression of inflammatory and destructive processes; prevention of tooth loss. The best prevention of complications of diabetes is regular monitoring of blood sugar in combination with careful oral hygiene and regular dental examinations. If a patient has diabetes, they need to: know how well their blood glucose levels are controlled and report this to the dentist at each visit; get advice from an endocrinologist before planning treatment for periodontal disease; make adjustments to diet or insulin regimen to improve metabolic control when planning intraoral surgery; do not plan non-urgent dental procedures if blood sugar is not well controlled. However, acute infectious and inflammatory processes such as abscesses should be treated immediately. Good diabetes control and oral hygiene are the best defenses against periodontal disease.

References.

1. Danilevskij N.F., Borisenko A.V. Zabolevanija parodonta. — Kiev: Zdorov'ja, 2000. — S. 218–236, 244–246.
2. Dedova L.N. Diagnostika boleznej periodonta: Ucheb.-metod. posobie. — Mn.: BGMU, 2004. — 62 s.
3. Dedova L.N. // Zdravoohranenie. — 2002. — №5. — S. 41–44.
4. Palij L.I. Izuchenie kliniko-immunologicheskikh osobennostej porazhenija parodonta u bol'nyh revmatoidnym artritom i razrabotka patogeneticheskoy terapii: Avtoref. dis. ... kand. med. nauk. — Minsk, 1989. — 15 s.
5. Povorozjuk V.V., Mazur I.P. Kostnaja sistema i zabolevanija parodonta — K., 2003. — 446 s.
6. Holodova E.A. Metodicheskie rekomendacii dlja prepodavatelej shkol saharnogo diabeta. — Minsk: NPK «Tehnologija», 2000.
7. Shepel'kevich A.P., Zabarovskaja Z.V. Vtorichnyj osteoporoz: jendokrinologicheskie voprosy. Diagnosticheskie podhody i principy lechenija: Ucheb.-metod. posobie. — Mn.: BGMU, 2002. — 20 s. 8. Shinkevich T.I. // Stomatologicheskij zhurnal. — 2001. — №1. — S. 27–28.
9. Cepov L.M., Nikolaev A.I., Miheeva E.A., Novikov V.I. // Parodontologija. — 2002. — №3. — S. 15–22. 1
0. Judina N.A. // Stomatologicheskij zhurnal. — №3. — S. 50–52.